

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

MODERNIZATIONS IN OTTOMAN TURKEY

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Abstract

First part of in this research, evaluations were made on Kochî Bey's Treatise and summary information was included. It was understood that the book was prepared in the form of a report resulting from a pause in the life of the Ottoman Empire in the 17th century.

Second part of in this research, evaluation made on the book titled "Modernization in Turkey", written by Niyazi Berkes (1908-Cyprus, 1988-USA), was published in 1973 and dedicated to the 50 years of the establishment of the Republic. During the years when N. Berkes was working as an academician at Mc.Graw Hill University in Canada; It consists of research prepared over a period of 2 years.

Final part of in this research, evaluations were made on summary evaluations on the "Cultural Changes" book examination written by social psychologist and historian Mumtaz Turhân, who lived in 1908-1969, are mentioned. In the work, Mumtaz Turhan evaluated the Ottoman attitudes towards Westernization and the West during the Ottoman Empire.

Keywords: Ottoman Empire, Modernisation, Constitutional Monarchy, II. Mahmut, II Abdulhamid, Entrance to Republic Period

I. A Summary Evaluation of Kochî Bey's Treatise (Zuhuri Danishman)

In this book evaluation; Evaluations were made on Kochî Bey's Treatise and summary information was included. Although we do not have much information about his life, it is understood that Kochî Bey was a state intellectual who was brought to Istanbul when he was a child and received education at the Ottoman Harp School (Enderun School).

It was understood that the book was prepared in the form of a report resulting from a pause in the life of the Ottoman Empire in the 17th century. The problems experienced in the Ottoman Age in the form of two separate reports written by Kochî Bey to the Ottoman Sultan Murad IV and then the second one and presented to Sultan İbrahim were described as a kind of criticism as solution methods. Another issue is that these reports, which formed the basis of reform in Ottoman social life, were criticized from time to time and were important when they were considered in the context of the beginning of a new spring of structuring.

Additionally, in this treatise mentioned; All the problems that occurred in the past were examined in detail, criticized and solution methods were tried to be found. The Treatise of Kochî Bey, which is important as the report presented to the sultan for the first time in the history of the Ottoman Empire, gained importance and was published by Sultan IV. In the first report presented to Murad, it was stated that the main basis of issues such as revenge, embezzlement, bribery and self-sufficiency that arose in Ottoman social life was actually the administration sitting in the state itself, and that these should be corrected.

In 1631, the main problems of the Ottoman Empire's administrative reign were touched upon, the organizational structure was criticized frankly, and issues that needed to be corrected were stated presented to

II. Sultan İbrahim. In the treatise report, it was emphasized that organizational problems in general and reform changes were necessary. In this treatise presented to both sultans, the importance of the treatise was also mentioned in the context of saving the treasury.

In fact, he mentioned that such problems emerged during the reign of Suleiman the Magnificent, and that problems occurred in Ottoman state and social life with the death of the Sultan. In addition, although the period of Suleiman the Magnificent is described in the treatise as a period in which social problems emerged, Ottoman economic life in his time (the economy) is experiencing the age of development; It was a period when the treasury was abundant and the reasons for this were also emphasized.

Evaluating the problems experienced in Ottoman life in a general context, Kochî Bey stated that in the sultanate, the military class, seyfiye, ulema ilmiye, bureaucracy, courtesy and kalemîye class praised themselves in the Sultan's peace of mind, kept duties, awards and ranks, and did not leave those who opposed those who did not allow their wishes close to the Sultan, and all of them became one. They gave slanderous information to the grand viziers and tried to increase the Sultan's power against those people. In this treatise, Kochî Bey also talked about the side effects of being alone in the palace on Ottoman social life. With this, Kochî Bey used this report as a mirror; He was able to honestly show Ottoman palace and social life to the Sultan. He was able to come to the Sultan as his most loyal staff, reached the highest rank he deserved, and helped him in his reforms.

Moreover, he did not leave him alone even during the Baghdad campaign. He even named Enderun "ecemi" and mentioned that all the problems stemmed from there and the reasons why those who came to the palace harmed the life of the Palace empire. He stated

that injustices in educational life in the context of institutions in the Ottoman Empire stemmed from the *ilmiye* class. Namely, Kochî Bey pointed out that the appointment of a certain group that had nothing to do with education through irregular rations was implemented, and that education in madrasahs was a bleeding wound due to the fact that the positions were taken over by the incompetent class with the laws dating back to the reign of Suleiman the Magnificent. He also stated that the *Usul-i Kanuni* too.

II. An Analytical Summary Evaluation with Comments and Opinions on Niyazi Berkes's (1908-1988) Book "Modernization in Turkey"

The book titled "Modernization in Turkey", written by Niyazi Berkes (1908-Cyprus, 1988-USA), was published in 1973 and dedicated to the 50 years of the establishment of the Republic. During the years when N. Berkes was working as an academician at Mc.Graw Hill University in Canada; It consists of research prepared over a period of 2 years.

In this work, the author, XVIII. the arrival of Turkish modernization with the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, the path that started from Ottoman nationalization during the transition from the Ottoman Empire Period to the Republican Period in the century; He talked about similarities and differentiations.

While reading this work in question, we see that the book is a work written with real meticulousness and intensity. N. Berkes completed this work abroad for 2 years and wrote it under the name "The Development of Secularism in Turkey". "Secularism", "used here has gained the meaning of modernization". In this book summary, we will touch upon N. Berkes' views on the reasons for modernization. Although the Secularism mentioned in the book reveals the concept of separation of religion from state administration, N. Berkes described this separation as 'liberation from sanctified traditions and modernization'. Referring to different eras of Turkey's history, the author put forward the thesis that "is the sanctification of tradition and culture in parallel with religion. He described the reason for this separation as the separation of religion from the sanctified tradition, not the separation of religion from the state. The author exemplified tradition as a turtle and the shell of this turtle as a religion, and stated that religion was sacred and caused it to continue in Turkish society in different ages and to get rid of the bad element of tradition. He also saw that modernization was implemented by keeping national-spiritual values alive in the context of national spiritual values, and the main theme of this began with the birth of nationalism.

He described nationalism as modernization resulting from changes in the world, and pointed out that modernization actually works together with religion. The author also touches upon conflicts in religion-state ties in Turkish society from time to time; He argued that the reasons for this were due to the inability of religious extremists in society to tolerate modernization.

In his book, Niyazi Berkes examined the changes that took place in Ottoman social life in different ages, the reasons for these changes, and also wrote about the Republican Era separately. The author wrote about the Ottoman Period and developed it against scientists who

thought of a religious state. Although the author made peace with the succession in the Ottoman Empire, he also stated that the state was governed more traditionally and that the theocratic structure was not included in the administration rather than the caliphate administration.

According to Berkes, although the Ottoman Age was in search of a new world, "did not accept the whole of Western Despotism", it kept its finger on the pulse of the world, but it was closer to the "Eastern Despotism" feature. In this structure, religion brought tradition to the people, but the people could not bring tradition to society. As an example, he exemplified the conquest of Istanbul by Fatih Sultan Mehmet, praised the birth of Suleiman the Magnificent, and described it as the period of the European Age.

The XVII century is the age of collapse; He stated that economic difficulties in the Ottoman Empire caused serious problems in the state, and he described the birth of reforms in the Ottoman Empire with the arrival of the XVIII century. According to Berkes, the age of westernization, which moved away from tradition, started from this date.

They called the XVIII century the age of industrialization of the Age in the West, praised N. Berkes and İbrahim Mütefferika, and saw the Ottoman education system as a bridge that brought together the West. Intellectuals such as Z. Gökalp and Y. Akçura have been described as philosophers and intellectuals of the Islamic age.

In the second part of the book, N. Berkes questioned history mostly with his ideas and analyzed it with his views. III. In the chapter, he explained the history from the Tanzimat, the Reform Edict, and the Constitutional Monarchy to the Republic. The period in which the Ottoman Empire needed westernization in order to gain industrial technology in order to strengthen the army was in the XVIII century. He mentioned that it ended in the last quarter of the century.

In 1770, Russia –was described as the date when westernization was opposed due to the European States supporting Russia due to the Ottoman wars. In the Ottoman Empire, III. was opposed during a reasonable transition period. He also talked about the Nizam-ı Cedid rebellion during the time of Sultan Selim.

Until the time of II. Sultan Mahmut, it was described as a period in Ottoman state and social life when nationalism did not come. According to Berkes, Sultan II. With the arrival of Mahmud's period; The Sheikh al-Islam, the head of the fatwa authorities, has now been set aside from the state administrative management mechanism. It has now been enriched with staff brought from abroad under the management of Sahiyye and Harbiye. The rules of law and sharia were reformed and separated from each other. French law was used in secularism. Tanzimat Period with the adoption of French law (II. Mahmut) left the sharia sultanate in the state administration. In 1858, the Ottoman Criminal law underwent a radical change and French law was adopted (the Nizamiye Court was transferred to the Ministry/Ministry of Justice, and the Sharia Courts were transferred to the control of the

Shaykh al-Islam). The draft or foundation of the concept of nationalism was laid in this period.

Educational curricula and programs have been radically changed, and students have been sent abroad (for example; France) for the purpose of implementing the overseas tradition. Two-looking structures dominated. One has been described as easternization, which preserves national-spiritual values, and the other has been described as westernization, remaining true to these values. In practice, Nâmîk Kemal and Şinâsi, who impressed the Sultan, were described as intellectuals and columnists of the period.

Later XIX. century The II. Payitaht Abdulhamit Period was described as a period that could not cope with thoughts and was harshly criticized. The reason for this is that it opposes the West, re-Islamization or sharia traditionalism. With the arrival of the Constitutional Monarchy Period in 1908, it was described as a period of focus on Islam and westernization, and the reason for this was seen in the formation of a new structure in state administration in the search for a nation state. On the other hand, it was stated that Mehmet Akif Ersoy, Abdullah Cevdet and Ziyâ Gökalp, who were described as philosophers of the period as intellectuals of Islamic thought, investigated the reasons for their falling behind in Europe, and that they saw the reasons for this not due to Islam but in the absence of nationalism and nationalism, and with this, a transition to nationalism in the Ottoman Empire was achieved. He stated that the time has arrived.

At the end of the II. Constitutional Monarchy period and the transition to the Republic period, the existence of a nation-state structure with a class of nationalists, Islamists and neutrals was mentioned. While the role of "Union and Progress in the Ottoman Empire was mentioned until 1918, with Islamization, the existence of the separation of the concept of nationalism in nationalism was now mentioned, and Ziya Gökalp's efforts were brought forward in this regard. "During the period when the Committee of Union and Progress was in government, sharia was completely separated from the state, the foundation of secularism was laid, and modernization was taken as a basis in this regard.

During this period, Niyazi Berkes mentioned that in family law, all sharia courts were taken from the sheikh al-Islam and given to the Ministry of Justice, and that women were given the right to divorce.

In addition, during this period, administrative administrations (branches controlling education) were now affiliated with the Ministry of Education (Ministry of National Education) and democratization was implemented. Arguing that the starting basis of the Tanzimat was the path that led to the Republic, Berkes pointed out that inconsistent double standards (problems) from the Tanzimat period were also seen in the Republican era.

Describing the acceptance of the National Peyman Treaty (Peyman-i Milli) and the dissolution of the Parliament in Istanbul as the arrival of the Mustafa Kemal Atatürk Era, the author is the biggest factor that differentiates it from the last period of the Ottoman

Empire, and is the nightmare in Turkey of the current modernization of Europe along with nationalization.

The complete separation of religion from the state was described by Berkes as the beginning of secularism. Atatürk's period towards modern Europe is shown as a state administration that accepts the nation state but is against the religious state. Providing information about the main purpose of the reforms, Berkes stated that the main reason for this was the path to contemporary westernization. While talking about the Republic period, Berkes concluded his book by describing secularism itself as modernization.

III. A Study on Mumtaz Turhân's Book on Cultural Changes

In this report, summary evaluations on the "Cultural Changes" examination written by social psychologist and historian Mumtaz Turhân, who lived in 1908-1969, are mentioned. In the work, Mumtaz Turhan evaluated the Ottoman attitudes towards Westernization and the West during the Ottoman Empire.

As a social psychologist, he wrote and made evaluations about cultural changes, starting from the Tulip Era that started in the Ottoman Empire with the Passarowitz Agreement of 1718, until the proclamation of the Republic of Turkey, which was established in 1923.

According to Mumtaz Turhân, cultural change is a collection of national, spiritual and material values, as well as related changes with the emerging elements in the life of the Ottoman society. The concept of culture is divided into two as the main theme in the book. They have been described as material and spiritual values. The author saw cultural changes as progress that affects social life.

He saw the meeting of two different cultures in the realization of cultural changes and the communication that supported it. However, the author, who opposed this view, underlined that culture will be subject to spontaneous change in the life of society. He described this as forced cultural changes and stated that it emerged as a result of internal imposition from his society. In this book, Turhan saw the process from village life to the beginning of the Tulip Era and then to the Republic as cultural change, progress, westernization and modernization. Comparing cultural changes with civilization, the author described cultural change as young. Turhan described the concept of civilization as a historical concept and saw it in the accumulated experiences of the society. He stated that each culture has its own uniqueness and that cultures change when they encounter this differentiation.

According to Turhan, the Tanzimat, Tulip Era, Constitutional Monarchy and Republic periods were cultural changes in Turkish social life in the context of westernization. For example, making legal regulations and revealing the concept of nationalism during the Constitutional Monarchy period was the beginning and implementation of cultural change in Ottoman social life at that time. However, according to Turhan, it is not possible to abandon the unique element of culture without change, material and spiritual change. In this

context, change has become a necessity for cultural changes to occur. For example, according to Turhan, the fact that Russians remained in the Ottoman Empire during the Ottoman-Russian Wars was a cultural change. The advent of new technology is a change. Pointing out that there was change in the Ottoman Empire in every age, Turhan also talked about the continuity of some national and spiritual values.

Turhan saw the key to westernization secularism in modernization from the Tulip Era to the Republic. He described the transition from the Republican period to the 1950s as Turkey's modernization, described it as a half-century in which the ideology of Westernism became widespread, and stated it as a period of revolution.

With this, Turhan concluded that cultural changes occur as differentiation and westernization that lead to progress in each time period, and that the concept of civilization is a more ancient, accumulated and applied set of spiritual values.

Summary

According to Kochî Bey, who assessed Ottoman issues generally, the military class, seyfiye, ulema ilmiye, bureaucracy, courtesy, and kalemîye class in the sultanate praised themselves in the Sultan's peace of mind, kept duties, awards, and ranks, and did not leave those who opposed those who did not allow their wishes close to the Sultan, and all of them became one. They attempted to strengthen the Sultan's authority against those individuals by providing the grand viziers with false information. Kochî Bey also discussed the consequences of isolation in the Ottoman palace for social life in this book. Kochî Bey utilized this report as a mirror, enabling him to candidly depict the Ottoman Palace.

However, Niyazi Berkes stated at this time that women were granted the right to divorce and that all sharia courts in family law had been transferred from

the sheikh al-Islam to the Ministry of Justice. Additionally, democratization was put into place at this time, and administrative administrations—the branches in charge of education—became affiliated with the Ministry of Education (Ministry of National Education).

Berkes said that the Tanzimat's foundation was the route that resulted in the Republic and that issues and conflicting double standards from the Tanzimat era persisted into the Republican era.

The author refers to the adoption of the National Peyman Treaty (Peyman-i Milli) and the dissolution of the Istanbul Parliament as the beginning of the Mustafa Kemal Atatürk Era.

The inception and implementation of a cultural shift in Ottoman social life occurred during the Constitutional Monarchy period. However, Turhan contends that change—both material and spiritual—is necessary in order to relinquish the distinctive aspect of culture. In this setting, it is now necessary for change to happen before cultural changes may happen. Turhan argues that one example of a shift in culture was the Russians' decision to stay in the Ottoman Empire during the Ottoman-Russian Wars. A change is the introduction of new technologies. While pointing out that the Ottoman Empire changed throughout history, Turhan also discussed how certain cultural and religious ideals remained constant. Turhan believed that industrialization from the Tulip Period to the Republic held the key to secularism in the West.

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